

Analyzing Antecedents of Customer Satisfaction and its Impact on Word Of Mouth Communication in Life Insurance Services

Author's Details

⁽¹⁾Anas Allahham – ⁽²⁾Asaad Aljumaa-

Marketing and International Trade Department-Higher Institute of Business Administration-Damascus - Syria

ABSTRACT:

Life insurance players have started realizing that their business depends on customer satisfaction, the purpose of this paper is to determine the antecedents and consequences of customer satisfaction in insurance services in Syria.

In order to accomplish objectives of this research, a model has been proposed to reflect the influence of Perceived service quality, price satisfaction on image on customer satisfaction, and word of mouth, the model is tested by structural equations and the final sample is 400 clients of four insurance institutions.

The findings Show that price satisfaction and image have a positive effect on customer satisfaction, and customer satisfaction has a positive effect on word-of- mouth.

If insurance services have to compete through customer satisfaction, it is proven by this paper that the construct which most influences customer satisfaction in insurance services is the price satisfaction constructs, also it is proven that if the image rises, the customer satisfaction will increase, which is a prerequisite for positive word of mouth.

KEY WORDS:

Insurance services, Service Quality, Perceived Value, Satisfaction, Price Satisfaction, image, WOM.

1. INTRODUCTION

The life insurance industry like many other financial services industries is facing a rapidly changing market, new technologies, economic uncertainties, fierce competition and more demanding customers and the changing climate has presented an unprecedented set of challenges. Just like companies of other business domains, life insurance also considers their customers as the most important asset. However, the most critical issue is whether this customer orientation is reflected in their strategies.

Life insurance providers increasingly recognize that today's customers who insist on improvements in quality of services have many alternatives, especially after the growing importance of life insurance during the crisis prevailing in Syria and, therefore, may more readily change providers if not satisfied. This is evident from the not so uncommon practice of policy lapses, readily embraced by dissatisfied policyholders. The decrease in customer loyalty has made management of service quality and customer satisfaction critically important factors for insurance players.

The life insurance providers need to reconfigure their strategy and business to sustain or improve their competitive advantage, and for this they first need to consider how to create a satisfied customer base that will not be eroded even in the face of fierce competition. For answering this fundamental question, these companies must realize the necessity of studying and understanding various antecedents and consequences of customer satisfaction.

2. PREVIOUS RESEARCH:

2.1. Antecedents of Customer Satisfaction:

2.1.1. Service Quality:

In today's world of intense competition, the key to sustainable competitive advantage lies in delivering high quality services that will in turn result in satisfied customers, therefore, there is not even an iota of doubt concerning the importance of service quality as the ultimate goal of service providers throughout the world. Many studies talked about the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction, (Fornell et al, 1996) concluded that service quality is one of the most important determinants of the American Customer Satisfaction, (Parasurman et al, 1988) show that service quality is the discrepancy between the expected service (ES) and perceived service (PS): (a) When $ES > PS$, perceived quality is less than satisfactory and will tend toward totally unacceptable quality, with increased discrepancy between ES and PS. (b) when $ES = PS$, perceived quality is satisfactory (c) when $ES < PS$, perceived quality is more than satisfactory and will tend toward ideal quality, with increased discrepancy between ES and PS. This leads to H1 and H2

H1: Service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

H2: Service quality has a positive effect on image.

2.1.2. Price Satisfaction:

Anderson & Mittal (2000) arrived at five dimensions of price satisfaction which are supplemented by Matzler (2004) with price fairness as a separate dimension:

- Price transparency:
Clear, comprehensive, current and effortless overview about a company's quoted prices.
- Price quality ratio:
Ratio or trade-off between quality of the service and monetary costs.
- Relative price:
Price of the offer compared to that of competitors.
- Price confidence:
Customers' certainty that the price is favorable.
- Price reliability:
Fulfillment of raised price expectations and prevention of negative "price surprises"
- Price fairness:
Consumers' perception of whether the difference between the socially accepted price and another

comparative party is reasonable, acceptable, or justifiable.
Literature on relationship marketing argues that there is positive relationship between the price satisfaction and perceived value (Matzler. et al, 2005). The companies that deliver higher value to the customers are more likely to satisfy them and to increase their loyalty (Zeithaml, 1988). Mittal (1998) refers to the different stages of consumers' decision making Processes in order to analyze which price dimensions affect global price satisfaction within the respective stages. From the customer's point of view, price problems will differ within the different stages (Figure 1). That leads to H3 and H4:

H3: Price satisfaction has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

H4: Price satisfaction has a positive effect on image

Figure (1) Phases in Decision Processes

2.1.3. Source: Adapted from Diller (1997)

2.1.4. Perceived Value:

Literature on relationship marketing argues that companies that deliver higher Value to the customers is more likely to satisfy them and to increase their loyalty. Customer value can be defined as "a consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perception of what is received and what is given" (Zeithaml, 1988), thus there is a "get" and a "give" component in the equation. While (Bolton & drew, 1991) show that a customer's assessment of value depends on sacrifice (i.e., the monetary and nonmonetary costs associated with utilizing the service), Customer characteristics, customer intention, while (Helgesen & Nettet, 2007) concluded that perceived value has a significant effect on customer satisfaction, this leads to H5.

H5: Perceived value has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

2.1.5. Image:

The influence of corporate image has been studied by many researchers, (Helegsen & Nettet, 2007) argue that an image is overall impression made on the minds of the public about a firm, while (Arpan. etal, 2003) argue that corporate image is related to the physical and behavioral attributes of the firm, such as business name, architecture, variety of products/services, and to the impression of quality communicated by each person interacting with the firm's clients, (Clow et al, 1997) referred that there are four determinants for image which are as follows: Tangibility, Price, Advertising & Word of Mouth. Also said that corporate image has a direct effect on customer satisfaction or indirectly through perceived service quality in both its functional and technical.

While (Palacio et al, 2002) concluded that image in all its components "the emotional and rational" has a significant effect on consumer satisfaction and loyalty. Consequently the corporate image is the overall perceptions and impressions about the organization, it also building a good corporate image is necessary to attract new customers and

retain the current once, also an image is one of the most important determinants of customer satisfaction and loyalty according to (Alves & Raposo, 2010), this leads to H6.

H6: Image has a positive effect on customer satisfaction

2.2. Consequences of Customer Satisfaction:

Word-of-Mouth:

Consumers engage in positive word of mouth behavior as well as seek positive word-of-mouth opinion on their choice of service provider; those seeking for advice are constrained by their lack of knowledge of the choices available and are dependent on professional expertise, especially in life-threatening situations (Calnan, 1995).

(Ennew. et al, 2000) suggested that WOM is particularly valuable for consumer service as it reduces the perceived risk in making a purchase decision.

In the financial services context, WOM is particularly valuable, especially when it originates from social contacts, because of their greater perceived reliability. (Ennew. et al, 2000), within the stream of services research, it has often been suggested that there is a relationship between satisfaction and the desire to make recommendations for the service providers (Parasuraman, etal, 1988). In addition, (Lovelock. et al, 1996) suggest that customer’s satisfaction and service quality promotes positive WOM.

Furthermore the likelihood of customers spreading WOM will depend on their satisfaction level for at least two reasons. First, the extent to which the product or service performance exceeds the customer’s expectations might motivate him or her to tell others about his or her positive experience. (Maxham, 2001). Second, to the extent that the customer’s expectations are not fulfilled, possibly creating a customer regret experience, this customer will engage in WOM behavior as a form of “venting” his or her negative emotions, such as anger and frustration, reducing anxiety, warning others, and/or seeking retaliation (Anderson, 1998).

Bowman and Narayandas (2001, p. 296) in their study, defined word of mouth as "whether customers tell anyone about their experience and for how many people are told if a customer engages in WOM behavior". This method has a drawback that, some customers who could not provide an exact number of people told, responded with the phrase “a lot.” Also, the ability to provide an accurate value for the number of people told might decline over a period of time. Therefore, in this present research the insurance institutions customers were asked about their potential future intention for a positive word-of-mouth intention with a two-item scale. That leads to H7:

H7: Customer satisfaction has a positive effect on word of mouth.

3. METHODOLOGY:

3.1. The Model:

The model to be tested (Figure 2) results from the hypotheses previously:

3.2. Sample’s Definition:

Emphasis was placed on one type of insurance services, a life insurance due to the circumstances which is going through in Syria In order to test the proposed model it was necessary to select a sample of clients from four insurance institutions in Damascus city – Syria. From the total number of 500 questionnaires distributed, 400 were returned valid for statistical analysis; the response rate was about 80%, profile of respondents shown in Table (1).

Table1: Profile of Respondents

		N	%
Gender	Male	320	80
	Female	80	20
	Total	400	100.0
Marital status	Single	70	17.5
	Married	330	82.5
	Total	400	100.0
Age	<30	37	9.25
	30-40	91	22.75
	40-50	168	42
	>50	104	26
	Total	400	100.0
per capita income (SP)	<20000	10	2.5
	20000-40000	85	21.25
	40000-60000	130	32.5
	>60000	175	43.75
	Total	400	100.0
Education level	Elementary	84	21
	Secondary	117	29.25
	University	132	33
	Higher studies	67	16.75
	Total	400	100.0

3.3. Method of Data Obtainment:

Given the intended objectives expected to be reached with this research, a survey using questionnaires was the chosen way for gathering data, thus, a questionnaire subdivided in 6 parts was drawn up: Sample characterization, Service Quality, Price Satisfaction, Perceived Value, Image, Customer Satisfaction and Word of Mouth. All measures used a seven-point Likert-type response format, with “strongly disagree” and “Strongly agree” as the anchors, perceived quality was measured using measurement Scale by twenty seven items adapted from (Taylor, 2001). Price satisfaction was measured by using a measurement by twenty eight items was used by (Matzler. et al, 2006). Image was measured by six items developed by (Aydin & Özer, 2005). Perceived value measured by two items used in the study of (Fornell, 1996). Satisfaction was assessed by eight items adapted from (Kenneth & Sweeney, 2007). Word of Mouth was assessed by two items adapted from (Zeithaml et al, 1996).

3.4. Analysis of Results:

Following the two stage modeling strategy and after confirming the acceptability of the measurement model, there then proceeded an estimation of the structural model. Table 2 presents the composed reliability of each of these constructs, that is the level of internal consistency for each construct, As can be observed, all constructs exceed the minimum reliability level of (0.6) recommended by (Mallhotra & Briks,2010).

Table 2 Construct Reliability

Construct	Item number	Reliability
Service quality	27	0.80
Satisfaction	8	0.82
Perceived value	2	0.70
Image	6	0.77
Price satisfaction	28	0.76
Word of mouth	2	0.65

In turn, Table 3 presents the various structural equations, as well as the determination coefficient (R^2) for each equation.

Table 3 Model Structural Equation

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Structural equations	R^2	T	Sig	Result
Service quality -----> Satisfaction	0.11	1.521	0.13	Not supported
Service quality -----> Image	0.21	1.73	0.5	Not supported
Price satisfaction -----> Image	0.23	1.84	0.8	Not supported
Perceived value -----> Satisfaction	0,036	4.739	0.589	Not supported
Price satisfaction -----> Satisfaction	0.50	7.089	0,005	Supported
Image -----> Satisfaction	0.35	4.737	0,004	Supported
Satisfaction -----> WOM	0.38	4.802	0,004	Supported

In turn, Table 3 presents the various structural equations, as well as the determination coefficient (R^2) for each equation. From analysis of the determination coefficients of the various structural equations present in Table 3, it was

found that price

Satisfaction has a most positive direct effect on satisfaction (0.50), also image has positive direct effect on satisfaction (0.35), table 3 shows that Satisfaction has a positive direct effect on Word of mouth (0.38).

4. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS:

This study demonstrated that the construct that most influences customer satisfaction in insurance services that of price satisfaction this has a direct effect of 0.50, in other words if the price satisfaction of rises or falls by a unit, satisfaction increases or decreases in a proportion of 0.50. It is possible to say that to measure and understand the price satisfaction is very important because of its influence over the customer satisfaction and loyalty formation process. If Syrian insurance institutions have to compete through customer satisfaction, the first step to take is to measure the price satisfaction held by customers, and the second step should be to ascertain how the constructed price satisfaction is formed and how it can be modified in order to better reflect the intended image. The results also showed that image has a positive impact on customer satisfaction, This means that corporate image plays an important role in keeping the customers and reduce the rates of customer Switching, Data analysis also suggests that if insurance institutions wants to benefit from positive word of mouth and the related positive outcomes, they should increased their customer satisfaction because the higher level of satisfaction with the insurance service providers will increase the willingness on the part of customers to engage in more positive WOM communications which is crucial in the attraction of new customers and retention of existing ones.

Furthermore, insurance institutions will be able to create new competitive advantages if they manage to understand the effects of customer satisfaction, to be the provision of positive word of mouth, this is particularly relevant for life

insurance services, which are highly intangible, and therefore as customers cannot easily evaluate the value of the services offered, it can be stimulated by positive WOM, and may serve as an important competitive advantage.

So the insurance institutions in Syria wishing to achieve competitive advantage through customer satisfaction must be focus on the determinants of customer satisfaction such as service quality by narrowing the gap between the expectations of the customer and perception. In this way, this research contributes towards deepening the knowledge about antecedents of customer satisfaction and its effect on word of mouth as a consequence, and how much importance for insurance institutions in retaining current clients and attracting new customers.

5. RESEARCH LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH:

In this paper, the effect of past experience and/or expectations has not been studied as antecedents of customer satisfaction, so a future area may search in the role of other determinants such as price satisfaction determinants and their impact on customer satisfaction, also suggested to study the effect of

past experience, interpersonal communication and WOM on service quality evaluation. On the other hand, it also the Switching behavior and retention have not been studied, so it might study the proposed antecedents in this paper and the reflected impacts on switching behavior and retention as consequences. Finally should extend this work to include the comparison between the levels of customer satisfaction at several services organizations.

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